

Agronomic characteristics

Shallow water		Knee-deep water				Semideep water				Deep water	
Transplanting		Transplanting		Direct sowing/transpl.		Direct sowing/transpl.		Direct sowing		Direct sowing	
Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage
Aug.-Sept.	Oct.-Nov.	Jul.-Sept.	Oct.-Nov.	Jul.-Sept.	Oct.-Nov.	June-Sept.	Oct.-Dec.	June-Sept.	Oct.-Dec.	May-Sept.	Oct.-Dec.
10-60cm	45-15cm	20-90cm	60-15cm	20-110cm	90-25cm	20-120cm	110-25cm	30-160cm	120-60cm	More than 160cm	
depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	
2.5-4.5 t/ha		2.5-3.5 t/ha		2.5-3.5 t/ha		2.5-3.0 t/ha		2.5-3.0 t/ha		2.0-3.0 t/ha	

Duration: E = early; M = medium; L = late. Grain quality: m = medium; mc = medium coarse; c = coarse. Kernel color: W = white; R = red.

The extent of adaptation (indicated by arrows) of the rice varieties and their yield potentialities in relation to varying depths and durations of waterlogged situations at vegetative (veg.) and maturing (mat.) stages under direct sown and transplanted conditions. Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Promising rice varieties for different types of low-lying waterlogged situations

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Several recommended rice varieties were tested under common water situations – shallow water, knee-deep water, semideep water, and deep water – at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, during the monsoon season of 1971 – 72. The varieties were evaluated for suitability to different types of waterlogged areas and to meet farmers’ needs. Eight specially constructed fields were used to study the plants growing at varying depths and varying duration of waterlogged situations. The soil was clay loam with pH of 6.9. No manure was applied.

The accompanying figure names some varieties that show promise for different

low-lying situations, their grain quality and duration characteristics, and their yield potentialities under direct-sown and transplanted conditions. Such information may help rice workers formulate effective recommendations for varietal suitability, choice of grain types, and time of harvest for different low-lying waterlogged situations.

Alternate sources of dwarfism

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Because most of the short-culmed varieties are derived from Dee-geo-woo-gen, scientists at CRRI are investigating possible alternate dwarf gene sources from Japan, China, and Indonesia, and are generating short-culmed lines through mutation. Japonicas are of particular interest among alternate dwarf gene sources.

Scientists at the Central Rice Research institute, Cuttack, India, are using as alternate dwarf gene sources japonica varieties such as Hoyoku an Shiranui (above) and Jikkoku.

Several stiff-strawed, photoperiod-insensitive, high-yielding varieties have already been developed at CRRRI by crossing Japanese varieties such as Jikkoku, Hoyoku, and Shiranui with tall indicas. These lines show strong resistance to blast and fair resistance to bacterial blight under field conditions.

They have thin, erect leaves, late leaf senescence, and high harvest indices. At several testing centers in India, japonica-indica hybrids outyielded existing high-yielding varieties.

High and stable average yields in rice and wheat are obtained in Japan and several European countries without

adopting dwarf varieties. Efficient plant types suited to different agroclimatic conditions can be developed independent of the dwarf gene. But the process will not be simple, because a constellation of characters must be assembled through hybridization involving several parents with desired characters.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Variability in amylose content of rice

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An increasing demand for high-quality rices in both the domestic and foreign markets has brought close cooperation among rice breeders and cereal chemists. Amylose, the linear component of starch in nonwaxy rice, is responsible for the texture of cooked rice and is the chief influence on the eating quality judgments of milled rice. The nonwaxy varieties contain from about 7 to 34 percent amylose of milled rice (dry weight) or from 8 to 37 percent of starch. Rice varieties may be grouped on the basis of their amylose contents into waxy (1–2% amylose), low amylose (8–19%),

intermediate amylose (20–25%), or high amylose (more than 25%). The amylose content of a rice variety may vary by as much as 6 percentage points. Intermediate-amylose varieties remain soft even after cooling and are widely preferred in such countries as the Philippines, Indonesia, Vietnam, Burma, and Pakistan.

Because of the wide variability in amylose content within a variety, screening for intermediate-amylose types in a breeding program presents serious problems. A study was, therefore, undertaken to examine the sources and magnitude of variability due to several nonheritable factors. The total variability was classified into three main groups: that due to the environment or the conditions under which the plant grows;

that due to the sample plants or the method by which grain samples are obtained; and that due to the measurement technique or the variation involved in the laboratory. Varieties or selections differing in amylose content were selected to gain maximum information on how varieties interact with the various factors studied. The Simplified Amylose Procedure employing the Auto Analyzer Method was used to determine amylose content. The analysis of variance technique was used in most phases of the study.

Amylose content of grain, like protein content, was affected by environment. Temperature was negatively correlated with amylose in the low-amylose rice but showed no distinct trend in either the high- or the intermediate-amylose rices. Nitrogen application tended to reduce the amylose content of rice: split application caused greater reduction than basal application. The large effects of interaction between variety and location indicated that the relative performance of the rices varied from one location to another. The variation in amylose content among panicles of the same hill was larger than that among hills as well as among bulk-samples within a hill. Twenty grains and 100 mg of rice flour were found to be the optimum sample sizes for rice grain and for ground rice, respectively, in the determination of amylose content. Milled rice from a Test Tube Miller gave lower amylose values than did milled rice from a McGill Miller No. 2. The variance component due to samples was consistently much higher than that due to determinations of the same sample. The relative magnitudes of the variations due to runs and due to determinations within samples, on the other hand, were not consistent for all varieties.

Amylose content, which is a major factor influencing judgments of eating quality of milled rice, varies widely not only among rices, as above, but even within a variety. The differences in amylose content are reflected in varying textures of the rices when cooked.